

NEW PEDAGOGICAL TECHNOLOGIES AND METHODS IN THE TEACHING PROCESS

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Abstract: *The term technology is derived from production, in which thousands of technological processes are designed. They are the key to achieving the desired results. When these technologies are used, the region and their executors change, but they still produce the product they need. Pedagogical technology will be developed to achieve this in the educational process.*

Keywords— special method, pedagogical technology, process, student’s ability, to study the topic, traditional methods, ability to speak fluently.

1. INTRODUCTION

Another unique feature of pedagogical technology is that a well-designed pedagogical technology can be taught well by any teacher, even if they are not knowledgeable. Because pedagogical technology is created by pedagogical scientists, their skills are reflected in the design of the technological process. As before, statements such as “the purpose of the lesson was not achieved for objective reasons” or “the lesson was created for unexpected reasons” and the like have no place in pedagogical technology.

Based on the above-mentioned features of pedagogical technologies, it can be explained as follows: Pedagogical technology is a new approach to the educational process, and pedagogy is an expression of social engineering consciousness. It is a social phenomenon associated with the development of an optimal lesson plan based on the technical capabilities of the pedagogical process and human technical thinking. This means that the role of pedagogical technologies in the teaching of social sciences and humanities is great. Without them, the goal can not be achieved.

In pedagogical technology, as well as a special method, the method of development, research is used. In the formation of independent free citizens it is necessary to train specialists with a certain amount of knowledge necessary for the national economy and entrepreneurs who seek solutions to various problems. In the upbringing of such people, the product of teaching typical actions and research methods that learn to find a way out of non-standard situations are compatible. Pedagogical technology makes good use of the range of methods we need:

The main difference between the traditional methods and techniques of pedagogical technology is that it is derived from the theory of complexes, which is subject to all the laws of this theory. Today, the teaching of foreign languages to students on the basis of modern pedagogical technologies, ie modern interactive methods, is becoming a topical issue in higher education. One of the main issues is the use of teaching skills in the process of teaching foreign languages, the effective organization of the teaching process, adaptation to educational

standards, raising to world standards, the perfect formation of knowledge and skills of teaching foreign languages to students. is one of the important factors in the learning process. Today, modern technologies for interactive teaching of foreign languages are being developed and used effectively in the teaching process.

2. MATERIAL AND METHODS

The main difference between modern interactive methods and traditional methods is that students are free in the process of learning foreign languages, think independently, have the opportunity to express their opinions, engage in discussions, communicate freely with the teacher.

In the process of teaching foreign languages on the basis of modern interactive methods, the following is done:

- Students plan and actively participate in the lessons;

Students work independently and consolidate their knowledge according to a set curriculum.

- Students engage in a discussion on the topic during the lesson and all actively participate in it;

- Students participate as partners in the selection and implementation of teaching methods, express their views;

- Students are provided with the opportunity to describe and explain their knowledge, that is, to share it with others;

Of course, in all of the above, students can achieve a step-by-step process of learning foreign languages through interactive methods.

The following technologies of interactive methods are widely used in foreign language learning today:

1. Interactive game mode.
2. Methods of active participation of students in pairs and in groups.
3. The method of mental observation.
4. Type of frontal training.
5. Aquarium method.

6. Brownian motion method.
7. Incomplete speech method.
8. How to take your place.
9. Discussion and other similar methods.

The interactive method of teaching foreign languages is based on the above-mentioned modern technologies, as a result of which the student's knowledge and skills of independent thinking and speaking are perfectly formed. Their freedom is created during the lesson, which means that students set their own goals and objectives, discuss, debate, and finally draw conclusions on the topic being studied.

In general, students play a leading role in the interactive method of teaching, which is determined by their excellent command of a foreign language, the ability to express themselves independently, that is, the ability to speak fluently.

In the early twentieth century, the American philosopher, psychologist and educator John Dewey argued that the student should be active, not the teacher, in the classroom. He argued that dry memorization of knowledge in a book does not lead to anything, but rather cools students from reading and corrupts their thinking. Dewey's major contribution to education is the "complete process of reasoning."

The founders of the Audiolingual Method are American Methodists Ch.K.Fris and R.Lodo, who use audio-visual and audio-visual methods of modern forms of the correct method in secondary schools in Uzbekistan. Audiolingual Latin "audio" means I hear, I listen, "lingua" means language, I hear the language, I listen.

Let's take an example of this method. For example: To give students an idea of the country where the language is being studied. During the lessons, students are first introduced to the border areas of France. Then the topics will be explained, such as the traditions and customs of the country, its customs and celebrities. They can be summarized and a diagram can be drawn up so that the reader can remember them. In the middle of the diagram, France, ie La France, is written in a circle. Lines are drawn at the edges of the circle to describe the countries, traditions and customs of France, celebrities, and each of them is highlighted.

Through this method, when we say France, the whole country is represented in the eyes of the reader. In addition, the use of various games in French language lessons is also good for language learning. French textbooks for beginners are a good example of this. The textbook contains a variety of puzzles, games, puzzles that encourage students to read, think, reason. Answers to puzzles in the textbook we find in the methodological manuals created for teachers. In conclusion, the use of different methods in teaching foreign languages is very effective. How interesting the lessons are, the interest of students in the language, modern pedagogical approaches to the pedagogical skills of the teacher, the focus of the educational process is the student's learning activities, the approximate design of the educational process, diagnostic accuracy and objective control of the outcome, the integrity of

the learning process, and so on. A high level of student performance is the ability to organize one's own learning activities, to make the will and activity the subject of the student's consciousness. The ability to set this goal independently is reflected in the ability to choose ways of doing things, to be able to agree with others within their own influences and relationships, and to coordinate work, self-control. This can be done through advanced learning technologies. For example: "I know. I want to know. I learned" method. This method allows students to assess the level of knowledge on specific topics. In the process of applying the method, it is possible to work with students in groups or in groups. The activity performed by is analyzed.

The advantage of using the method is that in this process, students develop the ability to study the topic in specific parts and to determine the logical connection and connection between the parts on the basis of analysis and synthesis.

The method of "working with red and green cards". It is very convenient to use this method when working with students in groups and in groups. The method can be used to organize quick Q&A sessions at the end of the session. The method is based on the organization of the following actions:

- A set of special cards is prepared by the teacher, which express the concepts that serve to illuminate the essence of the subject in a logical sequence.
- Each group is given a special set of cards and is tasked to place the card in a logical sequence based on the concepts in them;
- When the task is completed by the groups, the back of the card is erased and a special cover is opened to determine the correctness of the task.

3. CONCLUSION

It should be noted that the teaching profession, unlike other professions, involves a multifaceted responsibility, firstly, it is the formation of personality, that is, a deep knowledge of the human psyche, and secondly, all aspects of education. He must organize the educational process through the effective use of tools, methods and ways, that is, he must achieve the effectiveness of teaching, and thirdly, he must form his own qualities in the process of development of society and nature. The teacher must shape the personality of the younger generation in accordance with the requirements of society.

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